

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

WOMEN ACADEMICS AND THEIR SCIENTIFIC CONTRIBUTIONS IN ISLAMIC CIVILIZATION

Mursalova A.

*Ph.D., Azerbaijan Institute of Theology
Str. Nakchivani 6, Baku, Azerbaijan
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-7806-8353*

Abstract

Contrary to common opinion, Muslim women have had a significant historical presence. Muslim women are not undervalued as educators, scholars, hadiths, sufis, orators, preachers, mujahideen women, philanthropists, poets, authors, and administrators.

Hatice, the prophet Muhammad's first wife, was the first Muslim woman to be revered and accepted in social life. Aisha, on the other hand, might be regarded the first example of a woman who had a societal impact through education and engagement in political matters of the day, as well as religious information transmission. We have the information of a significant number of Muslim women with varying degrees of understanding who have been participating in the learning and teaching pattern since the Age of Bliss. There were female Companions in particular who distinguished out for their expert knowledge on certain areas. As previously said, the ability to read and write was an uncommon and immensely valued talent at the time. During the Companions, the Prophet's daughter Fatima, as well as Kuaybe and Rufeyde bint Sad. Women specializing in medical services, such as Utba al-Aslemiyye (d. 7/628) and Umm Sinan, as well as various occupations, may be identified. From the first century, ladies from the Ahl-i Beyt have held positions in scientific circles. Women learnt hadith and fikh among Ali-offspring, Fatimah's especially in the household, and passed it on to science students.

It is possible to obtain information about several women who were documented as hadith narrators or hadith narrators during the Tabiun, tebeu't-Tabiun, and subsequent centuries.

According to the Quran, the difference between men and women is an objective truth, thus Muslims cannot account for or reject it, neither in the Quran nor in the Prophet's practice, the inherent difference between men and women is more spiritual, moral, or intellectual than the other. There is no evidence that it is on a lower level.

Keywords: Muslim women, scientist females, religion, Islam, knowledge

The embrace of knowledge and its superiority over supererogatory devotion, the fact that scholars are regarded successors, the student also has the task of teaching, and the necessity of the integration of knowledge and deeds are among the issues that our Prophet highlighted. Unquestionably, Muslims are interested in science since "learning information is vital for every Muslim." That is an essential need, according to his order. Muslim women, contrary to common belief, have had a substantial historical presence. Muslim women are respected for their contributions as educators, scholars, hadiths, sufis, orators, preachers, mujahideen women, philanthropists, poets, authors, and administrators.

Hatija, Muhammad's first wife, was the first Muslim woman to be venerated and welcomed in society. It wouldn't be out of place to bury him as Hatice. In addition to his ancestry, character, and trade repute, Muhammad's first mentor can be evaluated. Hatije and Aisha, on the other hand, might be regarded the earliest examples of women who had a societal impact via education and engagement in political matters of the period, as well as religious information transmission.

We have the knowledge and experience of a large number of Muslim women of all levels of understanding who have been active in studying and teaching since the Age of Bliss. There were some female companions who stood out for their specialized expertise in specific areas. As previously said, being able to read and write

was a rare and extremely valued talent at the time. Again, Fatima, at the companions' time. Women who specialize in medical services, such as Utba al-Aslemiyye (d. 7/628) and Umm Sinan, may be found in poetry, such as Aisha, Kuaybe, and Rufeyde bint Sad, and in some careers. Aisha is the one thing that all companions, male and female, have in common. Its mission was to learn and transmit the Prophet's words, actions, and approvals [Aydar, Atalay, 2014, p. 13]. There are various female companions from whom hadiths have been reported in this respect. Without a doubt, Aisha was the companion with the most advanced scientific equipment among the companions. He related over 2200 hadiths. Aisha was instrumental in the founding of the Medina school, answering questions and finding answers to problems. She also mentored women in the scientific community [Nahwi, 2007, p. 22-30].

Ladies from the Ahl-i Beyt have held scientific posts since the first century. Women learnt hadith and fikh among Ali's descendants, particularly Fatimah's, and passed it on to science students. Among these are et-Tahire el-Hurretu't-takyye es-Seyyide and et-Tahire el-Hurretu't-takyye e Nefise bint el-Hasen b. Zayd b. Hasan b. Ali b. Ebi Talib died in 208/824. Nefise bint al-Hasen, who came to Egypt with her family, lived in the governor's residence and had guests twice a week [Nahwi, 2007, p. 273-276].

Bishr al-Hafi, Ahmed b. Hanbal, and Imam Shafii are among his guests. When Imam Shafii was in Egypt,

he had regular meetings with our Mother Nafise and learned hadiths from her. When Imam Shafii died, his body was taken to Sayyide Nefise's house, where he conducted his funeral prayer. Muslims now consider Nefise bint al-grave Hasen's to be a pilgrimage site.

Literate women are Shifa bint Abdillah and Hafsa bint Umar. Shifa bint Abdillah taught women in addition to teaching them to read and write. Reading rukye also allowed her to cure a variety of diseases. Allah's Messenger had requested that Hafsa teach this method of healing (Khayat M.H. (2003). *Woman in Islam and her role in human development*, p. 13).

Sumeyye, Umm Ayman Bereke, Umm Salama, Fatima bint Muhammad, Semra bint Nuhayk, who was an inspector of the bazaar and established herself in the fields of health and administration, Shifa bint Abdillah, who was appointed governor of the bazaar administration by Umar, come to mind as the first Islamic martyrs.

Zuhri, in particular, claims to have learned from Amre bint Abdirrahman, whom he describes as a "sea of wisdom." It should be mentioned that Amre was recognized as sika and hujjat in terms of jerh and ta'dil. As a result of this, Caliph Umar b. Abdulaziz issued an injunction demanding the drafting of Amre's narrations during the compilation of the hadiths. Umm Imran Aisha bint Talha b. was one of the renowned females. Ubeydullah et-Tamimiyya (d. 101/719) should be mentioned. Aisha bint Talha Arabic history and literature, particularly Hz She is a female scholar who rose to fame due to her understanding of the constellations, which she learned from Aisha.

It is possible to gather information on various women who were documented as hadith narrators or hadith narrators during the Tabiun, tebeu't-Tabiun, and following centuries. These ladies are a link in the line of hadith certificates that dates back to the companions. Emetu'l-Vahid bint el-Huseyn b. Smail el-Mehamili (d. 377/987), Kerime bint Ahmed b. Muhammed b. Hatim el-Merveziyye (d. 463/1070), Shühde bint Ahmed ed-Dineveriyye (d. 574/1178) and others [Hermansen, 2013, p. 45-59].

The companions also included the first Muslim women to actively participate in battle, carrying water, nursing, and fighting. Safiye bint Abdulmuttalip, Umeyye bint Kays, the Ben-i Gfar tribal ladies, Azde bint el Haris, and Havle bint el Ezver, also known as Kara Shuvari, are among them. Nusayba bint Kaab el Ensariye is the Prophet. The Prophet praised her valor at the Battle of Uhud, saying, "Wherever I glanced left or right in the Battle of Uhud, I saw him fighting." These are not the only problems they face in a male-dominated sector. On the other hand, Aisha el Makzumiye scales the city walls and unlocks the city gate, allowing Tark Bin Ziyad to conquer Cordoba.

Throughout history, many Abbasids, Turkish, Persian, Mongolian, and Indian Muslim women wielded political power. Shegeb, who temporarily governed the Abbasid realm, investigated public hunts submitted before him by administrators and judges. Radiye Begum, who controlled Delhi and supervised the administration, commanded the army and was well-known for her diplomacy. Sakandar Begum and his daughter governed the Principality of Bopal in Central India until

1901. Yemeni Queen Al-Udar led a full and busy life, from political administration to school building and management, from Yemeni security to charitable work, and even fighting for Egypt's defense.

Among the charitable females were Tuekan Hatun, Melik Shah's wife, Nur Cihan, Cihangir Shah's wife, Fatima Fahriyya, Benefshe er-Rumiya, who rejuvenated Baghdad, Bazm-i Alem Valida Sultan, and the Ottoman sultans who established foundations in their own time. Zubayda bint Jafer-i Mansur, the wife of the world's most powerful man, Harun Rashid, is one of the most powerful Muslim women known for their immense generosity and even inventions.

In the previous century, important figures included the Egyptian Zeynab al-Ghazali, the author Meryem Cemile, the Secretary General of the World Union of Muslim Women Hatice Hafaje, and the international name in the area of Islamic Social Services Hatije Hafaje. Academician and activist Ingri Mattson, as well as social sciences and economics specialist academic Maha Genaidi, are two of the most important and polar carriers of recent times. Muslim girl names that are popular.

Women were prominent and adored in Islam's early years, especially during the companions and Tabiun eras. Men approaching them and learning from them is considered natural. Muslims are not hesitant to respect women and learn from them. Such intelligent and learned females' names may be found in every aspect of Islamic science.

Sayyide Sara bint al-Sheikh Umar, for example, is a female scholar who lived in Damascus seven centuries ago in the study of kalam (theology). Amat el-Vahid is an outstanding Shafii female jurist in the subject of fikh (his death in the 377th year of Hijrah). His father, Ismail al Varak, and other experts taught him hadith and fikh. Amat, a Quran memory, is recognized as a specialist in inheritance, particularly in Shafii fikh. El-Barkani has compiled a list of fatwas. Fatima bint Abbas, who died in 714 Hijri, was a female jurist whose intellectual background astounded the famed theologian Ibn Taymiyya.

Women, especially in Syria and Egypt, benefited greatly from their lessons. He is depicted in the works as a jurist, scholar, promoter of lofty charges, mufti, incorrect, and unique for his period. He addresses numerous female poets and intellectuals while quoting al-great Suyuti's Arabic lexicon, al-Kamus, from six well-known Arab ladies. Aisha bint Abdallah al-Mekkiye, who authored a book on her family's history, and Safiya bint al-Murtada, a linguist, are among them. Safiye, who lived in the eighth century Hijri, is one of the names that has endured due to the numerous works she authored.

Another notable character is Fatima bint Suleyman b. Abdilkerim al-Ensariyye ed-Dimashkiyye (d. 708/1308). Her father educated Fatima the topic of recitation and hadith from an early age. Around a hundred hadiths from Damascus, Iraq, and the Hejaz areas, as well as his father, are said to have benefited Fatima bint Suleyman. Fatima, who dedicated her life to research, spent her money building madrasahs and lodges along this road [Siddiqi, 1993, p. 120-121].

Certainly, demonstrating women's distinctive place in Islam and Islamic cultural life, which is not well recognized today, does not do so in the framework of today's fashion discourses, western paradigms, and feminist methods. In short, the current modernization of Islam is not about westernizing Islam, but about its purpose. She also emphasizes that the participation of these women in science and social life, who played an important role in transmitting Islamic resources to future generations, does not contradict Islamic values, but rather that they live in accordance with Islam, do not oppose Islamic rules and values, and do not neglect the personal virtue required by religion while performing a social function.

In the notion that the Quran indicates a distinction between men and women, Muslims cannot explain or refute this difference, neither in the Quran nor in the Prophet's behavior. There is no indication that it is on a lesser level since he reminds us that women were equally interested in what Muhammad taught, that women were always there when he addressed the audience or pledged allegiance, and that they even wanted special sessions for women's particular queries. As a result, several hadiths can only be recited by women. Several hadiths were first passed down by female companions, notably Muhammad's wives.

Aishe was the first Muslim scholar lady to address an audience and gather pupils around her. It is known that Hafsa, Umm Darda, and Amra bint Abdurrahman were held in high regard during the companions' time, primarily as significant hadith transmitters, and Umm Darda's Caliph Muawiyah's son Iyas was designated an arbitrator on hadiths, favoring even the period's giants like Hasan Basri and Ibn-i Sirin.

We can see that female hadith scholars played an important role in the development of contemporary hadith knowledge, accounting for a quarter of the hadith corpus and the bulk of books written in the last centuries based on hadiths transmitted via women.

She notes that, theoretically, Islam does not ban women from receiving and educating women, and that women's scientific learning and teaching take place within the context of Islamic values rather than the rules imposed by other systems.

These ladies continued to teach science and were active everywhere they went, even when traveling. Fatima bint Saad al Hayr, who died in 600 Hijri, was one of them. He was schooled by his father, Sa'd, and afterwards by Abu Galip, Kadi Abu Bakr, and Yahya bin Banna, and he taught pupils in Damascus and Egypt. Zeyneb al-Makdisiyye was born in Kasyun, one of Imam Zahabi's instructors in the 8th century, and became a student of notable hadith scholars, giving lectures in cities such as Jerusalem, Egypt, and Medina.

One of the eight thousand Muslim female academics is Seyidet Nefise, a hafiz of Quran, tafsir, and hadith scholar who is considered as one of the great saints. Seyidet Nefise, one of Islam's most renowned women, was born in Mecca, grew up in Medina, went to Egypt, and passed down hadiths to Imam Shafii [Aydar, Atalay, 2014, p. 25].

In addition, there are also famous Muslim women like Ziyb an-Nisa Begum al-Hindiyye (d. 1702), Nusret

Begum Emin (d. 1983), Aisha Abdurrahman Bintush-Shati (d. 1998), Zaynab al-Gazali (d. 2005), Naile Hashim Sabri, Semra Kurun Chemegil, Nedjla Yasdiman, Fevkiyye Ash-Shirbini, Kamile binti Muhammad al-Kevari, Keriman Hamza, Hannan al-Lahham, Angelika Neuwirth, Miyade binti Kamil, who have spoken in the science of Quranic interpretation [Aydar, Atalay, 2014, p. 3-22].

Women's effort and intensity, notably in the science of hadith, were observed in all times, not just one. He went on to say that women have specialized in hadith throughout history, but they were not heard enough since they were not as regularly recorded in biographical dictionaries as their male counterparts. As a result, false assumptions were made that there were no female intellectuals and researchers in Islamic studies.

When we look at female hadith experts from the nineteenth century, we discover that some of them were given the designations Sittulvuzera and Sittularab: Umm Medjduddin Sittularab bint Abdulmedjid b. Hasan al-Adjemi (d. 675/1276), Ummul-Hayr Sittularab bint Yahya b. Kaymaz al-Kindiyye ed-Dimaskiyye (d. 684/1285), Sittulvuzera bint Ebul-Fazl Yahya b. Muhammed et-Taglibiyye ed-Dimaskiyye (d. 715/1316), Ummu Muhammed Sittulvuzera bint Umar b. Asad b. al-Munadjja ed-Dimaskiyye (d. 716/1316), Umm Muhammed Sittularab bint Seyfeddin Ali b. Radi Abdurrahman al-Makdisiyye (d. 734/1333), Umm Muhammad Sittulvuzera bint Muhammed b. Abdulkerum b. Osman el-Mardiniyye el-Mizziyye (d. 736/1336), Ummul-Hayr Sittularab Aishe bint Ali b. Ömer el-Himyeriyye es-Sanhadjiyye al-Misriyye (d. 739/1338), Umm Muhammad Sittularab bint Shemsiddin Muhammed b. Fahriddin Ali es-Salihiyye (d. 767/1366), Sittularab bint Ibrahim b. Muhammad al-Halebiyya (d. IX./XV) [Hermansen, 2013, p. 45-59].

Aisha bint Yusuf b. Ahmed b. Nasir al-Bauniyye ed-Dimashkiyye (d. 922/ 1516) is an important figure. Aisha bint Yusuf learnt the Quran and received mystic training from Sayyid Ismail al-Harizmi and Muhyiddin Yahya al-Urmevi when she was eight years old. Aisha bint Yusuf, a jurist, was given permission to give fatwas and lectures in Cairo. In Cairo, he exchanged poetry with Abdurrahim el-Abbasi, one of the city's most recognized authors.

Fatima bint Muhammad b. Ahmad es-Samarkandiyye of the VI. (XII.) century comes to mind as a faqih woman. Fatima bint Muhammad was born in Samarkand and received her education from her father, the Hanafi jurist Alaeddin es-Samarkandi (d. 539/1144). She is also skilled in calligraphy. He very certainly continued to issue fatwas after marrying Kasani. Another example of administrators' interest in female academics is Fatima bint Muhammed. The Atabeg of Aleppo and Damascus, Nureddin Mahmud Zengi, revered, conferred with, and consulted Fatima bint Muhammad for his fikh ideas.

Because women's modesty and isolation are prized more highly in Islamic morals, knowledge about women is not as prevalent as that of men, even if they are academics. This feature of Islamic civilization also limits the recording of numerous facts regarding wom-

en's private life and social activity. Their accomplishments in intellectual and social life are overlooked due to a lack of information in biographical resources. In places like as Baghdad, Damascus, and Cairo, there are many female academics and researchers. Ladies like Amat al-Gafur, a fikh and hadith scholar, and his father, Imam Ishaq al-Dihlawi, are significant in the field of hadith and jurisprudence in India. Hafiz Ibn Hajar lists one hundred and seventy well-known hadiths in the eighth century alone, whereas Ibn Fahd al-Makki mentions one hundred and thirty well-known hadiths in the ninth century.

Female transmitters are frequently seen to be more reliable than males in hadith transmissions; men are seldom assailed with multiple claims, but women are few. Women scholars have demonstrated their competence in every branch of science, which is the foundation of Islamic civilization, from recitation to fikh, literature to mathematics, and they have brought their gains, knowledge, and experiences to life in education and training by educating themselves to the best of their ability. At the same time, women who established madrasas, dervish lodges, hospitals, and libraries contributed significantly to Islamic civilization.

The acts of female intellectuals and jurists who lived during the time of the infallible imams were sanctioned by the Ahl al-Bayt. Rijal's writings mention a treatise of jurisprudence produced by Imam Zaynabidi's daughter.

Saida, a maidservant of Imam Jafar Sadiq, and Ummi-Ahmed, the daughter of Imam Musa Kazim, were both regarded intellectual women at the time. Imam Sadiq advised women of his day to seek religious guidance from Hamideyi-Musaffat, also known as "The Golden Lady."

Zurara ibn Ayu's sister, Ummi-Aswad, joined Imam Sadiq's disciples long before her brother, and she subsequently utilized evidence to persuade Zurara to follow in his footsteps (the position and fame of Zurara is known in the hadith science). Kulsum, Salim's daughter, who lived during Imam Reza's period, wrote a whole book on him.

Throughout the subsequent centuries, skilled academics and mujtahid women grew up in the homes of significant religious experts. Ummi-Ali, the wife of Muhammad ibn Makki Amuli, was a religious figure for women. She was also known as "Shahidi-awwal" ("The First Martyr"). His daughter, Ummul-Hasan Fatimah, passed down hadith from her father and others. Her contemporary monikers were "Lady Sheikh" and "Sattul-Mashaikh" (Lord of Masters). Shahidi advised women to use their Umm-Ali and Umm-Hasan knowledge. Daughters of eminent Islamic scholars Sadruddin Amuli, Dearullah Madjlisi, and Sharif Ruydashti produced and taught commentary on canonical hadith and fikh texts.

Amina Beyim was the wife of prominent scientist Muhammadsaleh Mazandarani and the sister of Allama Muhammadbagir Majlis, the creator of the "Biharul-Anwar" encyclopedia. According to legend, he helped his brother compile the Bihar al-hadiths. Anwar's When his wife encountered problems in her scientific studies, she would seek the assistance of Amina Bey.

Several renowned Islamic thinkers considered learning from women as both a deficiency and a source of pride. The great hadith scholar, Ibn Jawzi, reported various hadiths from his master, a lady named "Shahda." While Khatib Baghdadi stayed in Mecca, he spent five days reading Bukhari's "Sahih" in the class of an erudite woman named Karima Marwaziyya.

Mujtahid lady Seyyida Nusrat Beyim (1887-1984), often known as "Banu Amin," was widely recognized as one of the best scientists of our time. Banu, who resided in Isfahan, studied under Ayatollah Seyyid Muhammadali Najafabadi, one of the most eminent academics of the period, and wrote nine books on akeeda, law, history, morality, knowledge, and interpretation. When she was 40 years old, she received ijtehad authorization from the late Ayatollahs Seyyed Muhammadkazim Shirazi, Sheikh Abdulkarim Hairi, Seyyid Muhammadali Najafabadi, Ibrahim Istehbanati, Sheikh Muhammadreza Najafi, and others. The late Ayatollah Istahbanati observed of Banu Amin in the authorisation letter he wrote for her, "If women are like this lady, they would surely be superior to men."

It should be noted, however, that in the Islamic world for many centuries, a woman was not authorized to judge or act as a mujtahid for others.

According to Jafari jurisprudence, a woman might attain the position of mujtahid by studying religious studies. No one else has the authority to imitate him (i.e., to follow his rulings and fatwas). According to Islamic law, only a male mujtahid should be copied.

In the present world, Muslim women continue to contribute to research. Such instances are as follows:

Rehab Iman, a Muslim scholar with a bachelor's degree in architectural engineering and a master's degree in Sharia, claims that her Islamic beliefs pushed her to succeed in science.

Professor Samira Ibrahim Islam was named UNESCO Scientist of the Year in 2000. She contributed significantly to the growth of narcology. This woman has a number of significant academic positions in her own country of Saudi Arabia, in addition to working for the World Health Organization. Samira Shah recently presented at the International Conference on Machine Learning in Canada a new computer assisted learning approach developed at the Delhi Research Institute.

Prof. Dr. Bina Shaheen Siddiqi has made significant contributions to health and agriculture by researching local plant resources. She has over 250 scientific articles and many patents for the production of anti-carcinogenic pesticides. Bina Shaheen Siddiqi graduated from the University of Karachi with a PhD and a Master's degree (Pakistan).

To recapitulate, Islam has never denied women the freedom to learn and participate in specified activities. He, on the other hand, encouraged women to be educated like men and to take an active role in social and political life. It is also clear from the examples in the article that women have always had a presence in political and social life and continue to operate in a range of fields in the modern world. Nowadays, limiting or restricting women's rights to education and labor in many

communities is not due to religion, but rather to the contemporary political context and traditions.

References

1. Adhami Shaykh Abdullah. List of Muslim Female Scholars. Thoughts of a Hijabi. https://www.wikiwand.com/en/List_of_female_Islamic_scholars
2. Aydar H., Atalay M. (2014). Women commentators in Islamic history. *Bülent Ecevit University Theology Faculty Journal*, Volume 1, Issue 2, pp. 1-34 [Published in Turkish]
3. Hermansen Marcia (2013). *Muslima Theology: The Voice of Muslim Women Theologians*. Peter Lang (Peter-Lang-Verlagsgruppe). p. 23.
4. Khayat M.H. (2003). Woman in Islam and her role in human development. *World Health Organization Regional Office for the Eastern Mediterranean*, 30 p.
5. Nahwi Mohammad Akram (2007). *Al-Muhad-dithat: The women scholars in Islam*. London: Interface publications, 337 p.
6. Siddiqi Muhammad Zubayr (1993). *Women Scholars of Hadith. Hadith Literature, Its origin, Development and Special Features*. Cambridge: Islamic Texts Society. pp. 117–123.